

The Existence and Uniqueness of the Solution of a Diffusive Predator-Prey Model with Omnivory and General Nonlinear Functional Response

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Introduction

The dynamic interaction between predators and their prey has become a prominent issue in both ecology and mathematical ecology in recent times, owing to its universal occurrence and significance in population dynamics. Over the course of nearly thirty years, studies on predator-prey models have been established, and in light of observations and laboratory trials, more realistic models have been constructed (see [1-9]). Three species' predator-prey systems have been the subject of intriguing and striking research since the 1970s [10-14]. For instance, using the same biotic resource, Safuan [14] examined the Leslie-Gower predator-prey model $\frac{dx}{dt} = r_1x(1 - \frac{x}{K}) - axy$, $\frac{dy}{dt} = pzy - d_2y$.

$\frac{dz}{dt} = z(c - dx - ey)$, where $r_1, r_2, a, b, c, d, e, p$, and q are positive constants and populations of prey, predator, and biotic resource, respectively, are represented by functions $x(t), y(t)$, and $z(t)$. For additional information about the biological background of system (1.1), see [14] and the sources listed therein.

However, it is evident from the above model that the carrying capacities of the predator and prey are correlated with the population size of the biotic resource, meaning that the carrying capacities of the two species are dependent on the amount of biotic resource. At low densities, it exhibits slightly unique behaviour, which makes it impossible to linearize the model at the border equilibria. Thus, it is impossible to study the linear stability of boundary equilibria. In fact, this singularity adds a great deal to the model's diversity of dynamics and makes system analysis quite challenging. Actually, prey x and predator y will go to another population, but its expansion will be restricted, if this preferred food z is extremely insufficient. The carrying capacity of the model (1.1) is increased by a positive constant to produce the following modified Leslie-Gower omnivorous predator-prey model

(1.4)

r_2 e

Individuals in a species undergo continual spatial distribution changes as a result of a variety of factors during their evolutionary process. Consequently, it has been acknowledged that the spatial aspect of ecological interactions plays a significant role. Several spatial effects have been included to population models in recent years. Many studies extend the predator-prey model of ODE to the corresponding diffusive predator-prey model by integrating the diffusion components, taking into account the natural diffusion and inhibitory impact (see [15-36]).

Through the incorporation of diffusion into model (1.1) in [31], Jau examined the subsequent nonlinear diffusive Leslie-Gower model of predator-prey

where the densities of the prey, predator, and biotic resource at time t and location $x \in \Omega$ are represented by the variables $u(t, x), v(t, x)$, and $w(t, x)$, respectively. $\partial\Omega$ is C^1 -class, Ω is a bounded open set in R^n , and the Holder continuous functions on Ω are $u_0(x), v_0(x)$, and $w_0(x)$. The boundary $\partial\Omega$'s outward unit normal vector is represented by ν . According to the homogeneous Neumann border conditions, there is no population movement over the boundary, indicating that the predator-prey system is self-contained. He looked into whether there was a unique solution for system (1.3), and as a consequence, he came to the following conclusion [31].

Theorem A Suppose that constants $\epsilon, \alpha, \beta, M, N$ and K satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < \epsilon &\leq \min_{x \in \Omega} w_0(x), \alpha \geq \|w_0\|_{\infty}, \beta \geq \\ c, M &\geq \max_{x \in \Omega} \{ \|u_0\|_{\infty}, p\alpha e^{\beta T} \}, \\ N &\geq \max_{x \in \Omega} \{ \|v_0\|_{\infty}, \frac{r_2 + bM}{c - dM} q\alpha e^{\beta T}, 1 \} \\ K &\geq dM + eN - c, \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(0, 0, \epsilon e^{-kt}) \leq (u, v, w) \leq (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$ and the system (1.3) has a unique solution (u, v, w) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$.

The three species food web models of the predator-prey type that we will be focusing on in this research have an omnivorous apex predator, which is characterised as feeding on many trophic levels. This is actually a general component of terrestrial or marine food web ecological systems. As an illustration, consider the following: species w are plants, species u are herbivores, and species v eat both plants and other herbivores. As an additional illustration, tiny animals like lizards and birds devour a lot of spiders and herbivorous insects. Additional examples can be found in the intricate marine food web systems. The terms "trophic level omnivory," "intraguild predation," "higher order predation," and "hyperpredation" have all been used to describe this phenomenon [37]. Inspired by the previous research, we would want to examine the following diffusive modified Leslie-Gower predator-prey model with omnivory and general nonlinear functional response $\partial u \sim u \sim \partial v$ by adding the diffusion into the model (1.2).

$u(t, x)$, $v(t, x)$, and $w(t, x)$ are the densities of the prey, predator, and biotic resource at time t and position $x \in \Omega$, respectively. $u(0, x) = u_0(x)$, $v(0, x) = v_0(x)$, and $w(0, x) = w_0(x)$, $x \in \Omega$. With a general nonlinear functional response $\phi(u)$, the predator devours the prey and contributes to its growth at a rate $b\phi(u)$. The following presumptions are applied to the function $\phi(u)$, which Georgescu and Morosanu thoroughly examined in [38].

(G) For $u \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where $L \geq 0$, $\phi(u)$ of the C^1 -class is rising on $\mathbb{R}^+$, $\phi(0) = 0$, and $0 \leq \phi'(u) < L$.

It should be noted that if function $\phi(u)$ represents the Holling type II functional response, that is, $\phi(u) = au/(1 + hu)$, where a is the resource and intermediate consumer search rates and h is the corresponding clearance rate, or the search rate multiplied by the (ostensibly constant) handling time, then hypothesis (G) is satisfied.

In order to demonstrate the existence and uniqueness of the solution for the system (1.5) using the methods of the upper and lower solutions [39] and the semigroup theory [40, 41], we will expand on the analysis methodology of Jau [31] in this study. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. We shall present the idea of the higher and lower solutions in the remaining sections of this part. Assuming the existence of the lower solution and the upper solution, $u^* = (u^*, v^*, w^*)$, in Section 2.

For the problem (1.5), $u^* = (u^*, v^*, w^*)$, we will demonstrate the existence and uniqueness of the solution on the sector $\mathbb{R}^+ u^*, u^* \equiv \{u = (u, v, w) \in C(D^+ T); u^* \leq u \leq u^*\}$. Two upper and lower solutions to problem (1.5) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$, where T is an arbitrary positive number, are provided in Section 3. Next, we establish that the solution (u, v, w) to problem (1.5) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ exists and is unique. Conclusions are provided at the end of the paper in Section 4.

Let $u_1 = u$, $u_2 = v$, $u_3 = w$, $u_1,0 = u_0$, $u_2,0 = v_0$, $u_3,0 = w_0$, $L_1 = d_1 \Delta$, $L_2 = d_2 \Delta$, $L_3 = 0$, $B = \partial$, and so on in order to simplify the notations of the system (1.5).

$$f_1(u_1, u_2, u_3) = r_1 u_1 -$$

$$\phi(u_1) -$$

$$k_1 +$$

$$p u_3$$

$$r_2 u_2 -$$

$$f_2(u_1, u_2, u_3) = r_2 u_2 -$$

$$b \phi(u_1) -$$

$$k_2 +$$

$$q u_3$$

$$f_3(u_1, u_2, u_3) = cu_3 - du_1 u_3 - eu_2 u_3.$$

(1.6)

Assuming that T is an arbitrary positive number and that $DT = (0, T] \times \Omega$ and $ST = (0, T] \times \partial\Omega$, system (1.5) can be expressed as $(u_i)_t - Li_i = f_i(u_1, u_2, u_3)$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$, and $DT = (0, T] \times \Omega$.

In ST , $i = 1, 2$ $u_i(0, x) = u_i(0, x)$, in Ω , $i = 1, 2, 3$. $Bu_i(t, x) = 0$.

regarding every $(u_1, u_2, u_3) \in J_1 \times J_2 \times J_3$. According to this, for every $(u_1, u_2, u_3) \in J_1 \times J_2 \times J_3$, f_1 is monotone nonincreasing in u_2 and monotonous nondecreasing in u_3 , f_2 is monotone nondecreasing in u_1 and monotone nondecreasing in u_3 , and f_3 is monotone nonincreasing in u_1 and monotone nonincreasing in u_2 . For each $i = 1, 2, 3$, where $a_i + b_i = 2$, let $u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $f_i(u) = f_i(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi})$. Then, f_i is monotone nonincreasing in $[u]_{bi}$ and monotone nondecreasing in $[u]_{ai}$. The coupled upper and lower solutions of the system (1.7) are then defined as follows (see[39]).

Definition 1.1. If $u^{\sim 1}, u^{\sim 2}, u^{\sim 1}, u^{\sim 2} \in C(D^{\sim T}) \cap C_{1,2}(DT)$, $u^{\sim 3}, u^{\sim 3} \in C(D^{\sim T}) \cap C_{1,0}(DT)$, and $u^{\sim} \geq u^{\sim}$ (i.e., $u^{\sim 2} \geq u^{\sim 1}$) with $u^{\sim 3}(t, x) > 0$ in $DT = [0, T] \times \Omega^{\sim}$, and $(u^{\sim i})_t - Li^{\sim i} - f_i(u^{\sim i}, [u^{\sim}]_{ai}, [u^{\sim}]_{bi}) \geq 0$, in DT , $i = 1, 2, 3$.

$(u^{\sim i})_t - Li^{\sim i} - filn DT$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$, $(u^{\sim i}, [u^{\sim}]_{ai}, [u^{\sim}]_{bi}) \leq 0$.

On ST , $i = 1, 2$ $u^{\sim i}(0, x) \geq u_i(0, x) \geq u^{\sim i}(0, x)$, in Ω , $i = 1, 2, 3$. $Bu^{\sim i}(t, x) \geq 0 \geq Bu^{\sim i}(t, x)$.(1.9)

We define the sector $\mathbb{Z}u^{\sim}, u^{\sim} \equiv \{u = \text{for a given pair of connected upper and lower solutions, } u^{\sim}, u^{\sim}\}$.

$(v, w) \in C(D^{\sim T})$: $u^{\sim} \{ \leq u \leq u^{\sim} \}$. Suppose that $c_1 = 2r_1u^{\sim 1} + Lu^{\sim 2} - r_1$, and $c_1^{\sim 3} = 2r_2u^{\sim 2} + b\phi(u^{\sim 1}) - r_2, 2^{\sim 3}$.

$Du^{\sim 1} + eu^{\sim 2} - c = c_3$. Therefore, for any i between 1 and 3, $c_i \in C(D^{\sim T})$. Applying the differential mean value theorem, we can readily deduce that, for every $u^{\sim 1} \leq v_1 \leq u_1 \leq u^{\sim 1}$, $f_1(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_1(v_1, u_2, u_3) = r_1(u_1 - v_1) - r_1(u_1 + v_1)(u_1 - v_1)$

$r_1(u_1 - v_1) - r_1(u_1 + v_1)(u_1 - v_1) = 1^{\sim 3} - (\phi(u^{\sim 1}) - \phi(v^{\sim 1}))u_2$

$1^{\sim 3} - \phi'(\xi)(u_1 - v_1)u_2 \geq (r_1 - 2r_1u^{\sim 1} - Lu^{\sim 2})(u_1 - v_1) - c_1(u_1 - v_1) = 1^{\sim 3}$

where (v_1, u_1) is the range of ξ .

For $u^{\sim 2} \leq v_2 \leq u_2 \leq u^{\sim 2}$, we can similarly derive that $f_2(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_2(u_1, v_2, u_3) = r_2(u_2 - v_2) - r_2(u_2 + v_2)(u_2 - v_2)$

$2^{\sim 3} + b\phi(u_1)(u_2 - v_2) \geq (r_2 - 2r_2u^{\sim 2} + b\phi(u^{\sim 1}))(u_2 - v_2)$, and for $u^{\sim 3} \leq v_3 \leq u_3 \leq u^{\sim 3}$, $f_3(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_3(u_1, u_2, v_3) \geq -c_3(u_3 - v_3)$.

It is therefore demonstrated that for any $u^{\sim i} \leq v_i \leq u_i \leq u^{\sim i}$, $f_i(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) - f_i(v_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) \geq -c_i(u_i - v_i)$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$.(1.10) Consider the following: $c_1 = r_1 - 2r_1u^{\sim 1}$, $c_2 = r_2 - 2r_2u^{\sim 2} + b\phi(u^{\sim 1})$, $c_3 = c - du^{\sim 1} - eu^{\sim 2}$. As a result, for each $i = 1, 2, 3$, $c_i \in C(D^{\sim T})$ $k_1 + pu^{\sim 3} + k_2 + qu^{\sim 3}$. Using the differential mean value theorem, we can quickly determine that, for each $u^{\sim 1} \leq v_1 \leq u_1 < u^{\sim 1}$, $f_1(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_1(v_1, u_2, u_3) = r_1(u_1 - v_1) - r_1(u_1 + v_1)(u_1 - v_1)$

One-third $-(\phi(u^{\sim 1}) - \phi(v^{\sim 1}))r_1(u_1 - v_1) - r_1(u_1 + v_1)(u_1 - v_1)$ equals u_2 .

$1^{\sim 3} - \phi'(\xi)(u_1 - v_1)u_2 \leq (r_1 - 2r_1u^{\sim 1})(u_1 - v_1)$

Where $\xi \in (v_1, u_1)$, $1^{\sim 3} = c_1(u_1 - v_1)$.

For $u^{\sim 2} \leq v_2 \leq u_2 \leq u^{\sim 2}$, we can similarly derive that $f_2(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_2(u_1, v_2, u_3) = r_2(u_2 - v_2) - r_2(u_2 + v_2)(u_2 - v_2)$

$(r_2 - 2r_2u^{\sim 2} + b\phi(u^{\sim 1}))(u_2 - v_2) = 2^{\sim 3} + b\phi(u_1)(u_2 - v_2)$

$2^{\sim 3} = c_2(u_2 - v_2)$, and $f_3(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_3(u_1, u_2, v_3) < c_3(u_3 - v_3)$ for $u^{\sim 3} \leq v_3 \leq u_3 \leq u^{\sim 3}$.

Consequently, we establish that for each $c_i \in C(D^{\sim T})$, such that $u^{\sim i} \leq v_i \leq u_i \leq u^{\sim i}$,

(1.11) $r_1pu^{\sim 2} = f_i(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) - f_i(v_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) \leq c_i(u_i - v_i)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

For each $i = 1, 2, 3$, and $K_{1,2} = \phi(u^{\sim 1})$, $K_{1,3} = r_2qu^{\sim 2} \sim 1$, $K_{2,1} = bLu^{\sim 2}$, $K_{2,3} = 1^{\sim 3}$, let $K_{i,j} = |c_i| + |c_j|$.

$2^{\sim 2}$, $K_i = K_{i,1} + K_{i,2} + K_{i,3}$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, and $K_{3,1} = du^{\sim 3}$ on $D^{\sim T}$. $K_{3,2} = eu^{\sim 3}$. Thus, for any $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, $2^{\sim 3} K_{i,j} \in C(D^{\sim T})$ and $K_i \in C(D^{\sim T})$, indicating that $K_{i,j}$, and K_i are bounded functions in $D^{\sim T}$.

It derives from

for all $i = 1$ through 3. For $u \in \mathbb{Z}u^{\sim}, u^{\sim}$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, this inequality demonstrates that f_i meets the Lipschitz condition. Additionally, f_i is a holder continuous function with $i = 1, 2$, and 3 on $(t, x) \in D^{\sim T}$.

The differential equations in system (1.7) can be expressed as $(u_i)_t - Li_i + ci_i = Fi(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi})$, in DT , $i = 1, 2, 3$. Let $Fi(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) = f_i(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) + ci_i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Lemma 8.1 in [39] gives us the lemma that follows.

Lemma 1.2. We indicate that $Fi(u)(t, x) = Fi(u(t, x))$ on $D^{\sim T}$ for each $u \in \mathbb{Z}u^{\sim}, u^{\sim}$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$. For all $i = 1, 2, 3$, the function $Fi(u)$ is Holder continuous in DT if $u \in C\alpha(DT)$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Furthermore, assuming that $u \geq v$ and that $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}u^{\sim}, u^{\sim}$, $Fi(u_i, [u]_{ai}, [v]_{bi}) - Fi(v_i, [v]_{ai}, [u]_{bi}) \geq 0$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Existence and Uniqueness of the Solution on $\langle \hat{u}, \hat{u} \rangle$

The upper solution $u^* = (u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3)$ and lower solution $u_* = (u_*_1, u_*_2, u_*_3)$ of the system (1.7) are always assumed to exist in this section. For every $i = 1, 2, 3$, let $A_{iij} = (a_{ij})_t - L_{iij} + c_{iij}$. The two starting iterations are $u^*(0) = u^*$ and $u_*(0) = u_*$. From the iteration process, we create the maximal and minimal sequences $u^*(k) = (u^*_1(k), u^*_2(k), u^*_3(k))$, $u_*(k) = (u_*_1(k), u_*_2(k), u_*_3(k))$.

1 2 3 1 2 3

In DT, where $i = 1, 2, 3$, $i^* \sim i \sim i^*$, $A_{iij}(k) = F_i(u^*(k-1), [u^*(k-1)]_a, [u^*(k-1)]_b)$

$A_{iij}(k) = F_i(u_*(k-1), [u_*(k-1)]_a, [u_*(k-1)]_b)$ in DT, $i = 1, 2, 3$, $i^* \sim i \sim i^*$ $B_{iij}(k)(t, x) = B_{iij}(k)(t, x) = 0$ on ST, $i = 1, 2, 3$, $i^* \sim i \sim i^*$ $u^*(k)(0, x) = u_*(k)(0, x)$ in Ω , $i = 1, 2, 3$.

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We first express the following positive lemmas, which were stated in [39], before demonstrating the monotone property of the maximal and minimal sequences.

Lemma 2.1: Let $u \in C(D^*T) \cap C^{1,2}(DT)$ be such that $\partial_t u - \alpha \Delta u + \beta u \geq 0$, for all $0 < t \leq T$, $x \in \Omega$, $\partial_t \partial u(t, x) \geq 0$, for all $0 < t \leq T$, $x \in \partial\Omega$, $\partial_v u(0, x) \geq 0$, for $x \in \Omega$, where $\alpha > 0$ and $\beta = \beta(t, x)$ is a bounded function in $DT = (0, T] \times \Omega$. In DT, then $u(t, x) \geq 0$. Furthermore, unless it is also zero in DT, $u(t, x) > 0$ in DT.

Lemma 2.2: Assume that $u \in C(D^*T) \cap C^{1,2}(DT)$ and that for any $t \leq T$, $x \in \Omega$, $\partial_t u(0, x) \geq 0$, for $x \in \Omega$, where $\beta = \beta(t, x)$ is a bounded function in $DT = (0, T] \times \Omega$. In DT, then $u(t, x) \geq 0$. Furthermore, unless it is also zero in DT, $u(t, x) > 0$ in DT.

We will now demonstrate the maximal and minimal sequences' monotone quality, which allows us to derive the following theorem.

Theorem 2.3. Let us assume the following: $u^* = (u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3)$ and $u_* = (u_*_1, u_*_2, u_*_3)$ are Holder continuous in x , uniformly in DT; $u_{1,0}, u_{2,0}$ are Holder continuous on the domain Ω^* satisfying the boundary condition at $t = 0$; $u_{3,0}$ is Holder continuous on the domain Ω^* . Then, for any k , the maximal and minimal sequences $\{u^*(k)\}$, $\{u_*(k)\}$ are well-defined on DT and have the monotone property $u^* \leq u^*(k) \leq u^*(k+1) \leq u^*(k+1) \leq u^*(k) \leq u_*$, (2.1) in DT. Additionally, $u^*(k)$ and $u_*(k)$ are connected upper and lower solutions of the system for each integer k (1.7).

Evidence. Since the proof for Theorem 2.3 is identical to that found in [31], it is not included here.

The pointwise (and componentwise) limits $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} u^*(k)(t, x) = u^*(t, x)$, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} u_*(k)(t, x) = u_*(t, x)$ are due to the monotone property.(2.2)

In DT, $k \rightarrow \infty$ exist and meet the connection $u^* \leq u \leq u_*$. We need to demonstrate that $u \leq u^*$ in DT in

order to demonstrate that the system (1.7) has a unique solution in $\mathbb{R}^3 u^*, u_*$.

Remark 2.4. Assume that the system's connected upper and lower solutions are u^* and u_* (1.7). The system (1.7) has a unique solution, u^* , and $u^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 u^*, u_*$. Furthermore, the iteration process with starting iterations $u^*(0) = u^*$ and $u_*(0) = u_*$ yields sequences $u^*(k), u_*(k)$ that both converge monotonically to u^* .

Evidence. Since the proof for Theorem 2.4 is identical to that found in [31], it is not included here.

Existence and Uniqueness of Solution of System (1.5)

- First, we shall demonstrate that the system (1.5) on $D^*T = [0, T] \times \Omega^*$ has both upper and lower solutions. It is demonstrated that the system(1.5) solution exists on D^*T . Next, we'll demonstrate the system(1.5) solution's uniqueness on D^*T . As a result, the system (1.5) has a unique solution on D^*T , where T is any positive integer.

- Conclusion 3.1. Assume that constants α, β, M , and N meet the following conditions: $\alpha \geq u_{3,0} \infty, \beta \geq c, M \geq \max\{\|u_{1,0}\| \infty, k_1 + \rho \alpha \beta T\}$,(3.1)

- The upper and lower coupled solutions of the system (1.7) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^*$ are then two functions $(u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3) = (M, N, \alpha \beta t)$, $(u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3) = (0, 0, 0)$. Moreover, Holder continuous in x , uniformly in D^*T , are $u^* = (u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3)$ and $u_* = (u^*_1, u^*_2, u^*_3)$.

- Evidence. We have $u^*_1(t, x) = 0 \leq M = u^*_1(t, x)$, $u^*_2(t, x) = 0 \leq N = u^*_2(t, x)$, $u^*_3(t, x) = 0 \leq \{\partial_v u^*_3\}$ because $u^*_1 = M, u^*_1 = 0, u^*_2 = N, u^*_2 = 0$, and $u^*_3 = \alpha \beta t, u^*_3 = 0$.

- $u^*_1(0, x) = 0 \leq u_{1,0}(x) \leq \max\{u_{1,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\} \leq M = u^*_1(0, x)$ is the result of $M \geq u_{1,0} \infty = \max\{u_{1,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\}$, $u^*_1 = 0$.

- Similarly, we have $u^*_2(0, x) = 0 \leq u_{2,0}(x) < \max\{u_{2,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\} \leq M = u^*_2(0, x)$ from $N \geq u_{2,0} \infty = \max\{u_{2,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\}$, $u^*_2 = 0$.

- We can determine that $u^*_3(0, x) = 0 \leq u_{3,0}(x) \leq \max\{u_{3,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\} \leq \alpha = u^*_3(0, x)$ from $\alpha \geq u_{3,0} \infty = \max\{u_{3,0}(x), x \in \Omega^*\}$, $u^*_3 = 0$.

- Thus, the upper and lower coupled solutions of the system (1.7) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ are represented by a pair of functions $(\tilde{u}_1, \tilde{u}_2, \tilde{u}_3) = (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$, $(\hat{u}_1, \hat{u}_2, \hat{u}_3) = (0, 0, 0)$. The proof is finished.
- The following result is easily obtained from Theorem 3.1.
- Conclusion 3.2. Assume α, β, M , and N are constants that fulfil $\alpha \geq w_0 \infty$, $\beta \geq c$, $M \geq \max\{\|u_0 \infty, k_1 + \rho \alpha e^{\beta T}\}$,
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- $$N = \max\{\|v, r_2 + b\phi(M)(k) + q\alpha e^{\beta T}\}, (3.2)$$
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- $0 \infty 2$
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- Afterwards, the upper and lower coupled solutions of the system (1.5) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ are represented by a pair of functions $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w}) = (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$, $(\hat{u}, \hat{v}, \hat{w}) = (0, 0, 0)$. Moreover, Holder continuous in x , uniformly in D^-T , are $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w})$ and $(\hat{u}, \hat{v}, \hat{w})$.
- We shall now demonstrate that the unique solution $\tilde{u} \sim \tilde{v} \sim \tilde{w}$ of the system (1.7) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ is the limit of the maximum and minimum sequences $u^-(k) = (u^-(k), u^-(k), u^-(k))$, $u(k) = \tilde{u} \sim \tilde{v} \sim \tilde{w}$ $(u(k), u(k), u(k))$ with initial iterations $u^-(0) = (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$ and $u(0) = (0, 0, 0)$.
- Theorem 3. Assuming (3.1) is true, there exists a unique solution (u_1, u_2, u_3) for the system (1.7) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$, and $(0, 0, 0) \leq (u_1, u_2, u_3) \leq (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$.
- Evidence. Assuming that the solutions of the system (1.7) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ are (u_1, u_2, u_3) and (v_1, v_2, v_3) , there exists a positive number M_0 such that $(0, 0, 0) < (u_1, u_2, u_3)$, and $(v_1, v_2, v_3) \leq (M_0, M_0, M_0)$.
- A comparable demonstration of (1.12) in Section 1 allows us to quickly determine that constants K^i , where $i = 1, 2$, and 3 , exist such that
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- Given that $\|f_i(u_1, u_2, u_3) - f_i(v_1, v_2, v_3)\| \leq K^i(\|u_1 - v_1\| + \|u_2 - v_2\| + \|u_3 - v_3\|)$.
-
- $(u_1)_t - d_1 \Delta u_1 = f_1(u_1, u_2, u_3)$, $(u_2)_t - d_2 \Delta u_2 = f_2(u_1, u_2, u_3)$, $(u_3)_t = f_3(u_1, u_2, u_3)$, $(v_1)_t - d_1 \Delta v_1 = f_1(v_1, v_2, v_3)$, $(v_2)_t - d_2 \Delta v_2 = f_2(v_1, v_2, v_3)$, $(v_3)_t = f_3(v_1, v_2, v_3)$,
-
- as well as the starting and boundary conditions
- $\partial v_i(t, x) = 0$, $x \in \partial \Omega$, $t > 0$, $i = 1, 2$, $\partial v_i \sim \partial v_i$ $u_i(0, x) = v_i(0, x) = u_i, 0(x)$, $x \in \Omega$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.
- For every t in $[0, T]$ and every x in Ω^- , let $u_i(t)(x) = u_i(t, x)$ and $v_i(t)(x) = v_i(t, x)$. We can readily obtain that $u_1(t) - v_1(t) + u_2(t) - v_2(t) + u_3(t) - v_3(t) = u_1(s) - v_1(s) + u_2(s) - v_2(s) + u_3(s) - v_3(s) \infty t \leq (K_1 + K_2 + K_3) \int_0^t (u_1(s) - v_1(s) + u_2(s) - v_2(s) + u_3(s) - v_3(s)) ds$.
- Gronwall's inequality thus gives us $u_i(t, x) = v_i(t, x)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, for any t in the interval $[0, T]$ and x in the interval Ω^- . The system (1.7) has a unique solution (u_1, u_2, u_3) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$, and $(0, 0, 0) \leq (u_1, u_2, u_3) \leq (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$, according to Theorems 2.4 and 3.1.
- The following result is easily obtained from Theorem 3.3.
- Theme 3.4. If equation (3.1) is true, then there is only one solution (u, v, w) for the system (1.5) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$, and $(0, 0, 0) \leq (u, v, w) \leq (M, N, \alpha e^{\beta t})$.

Conclusion

This research examines a modified Leslie-Gower food web model with three species, featuring omnivory—defined as feeding on more than one trophic level—and general nonlinear functional response.

degree. The biotic resource's population size plus a constant determines the model's carrying capacity. Jau also examined a three-species Leslie-Gower food web model (1.3) in [11] using the same biotic

resource; however, the model's carrying capacity is only proportionate to the biotic resource's population size without the addition of a constant. At low densities, it exhibits slightly unique behaviour, which makes it impossible to linearize the model at the border equilibria. In fact, the analysis of the system is greatly complicated by this singularity (1.3). As a result, the model takes omnivory into account (1.5). Using the techniques of upper and lower solutions along with semigroup theory, we can determine that if (3.1) is true, then there is only one solution (u, v, w) for the system (1.5) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$ and $(0, 0, 0) \leq (u_1, u_2, u_3) \leq (M, N, \alpha\epsilon t)$.

According to Jau's findings in [11], if (1.4) is true, then there exists a unique solution (u, v, w) for the system (1.3) on $[0, T] \times \Omega^-$, and $(0, 0, \epsilon\epsilon - Kt) < (u, v, w) \leq (M, N, \alpha\epsilon\beta t)$.

Clearly, compared to condition (1.4), condition (3.1) is weaker and simpler. Additionally, our paper's scope of solutions is greater than that of [11]. From the explanation above, it is clear that omnivory has a significant impact on the system's uniqueness and existence (1.5). Indeed, several Artiodactyla species are omnivores; they include wild boar, which mostly eats grass, sweet potatoes, roots, tubers, and wild fruit. Because they can consume a variety of foods, if one type of food is scarce, like wild fruit, they can eat sweet potatoes instead, which will help them survive in the harsh environment.

Indeed, the system (1.5) can be changed to the system (1.3) if $k_i \rightarrow 0$, $i = 1, 2$, and $\phi(u) = au$. As a result, when examining system (1.5), we can clearly observe more dynamic behaviours of system (1.3). One of the primary findings of Jau's study [Jau GC. The challenge of the nonlinear diffusive predator-prey model with the same biotic resource] is demonstrated to be complemented and enhanced by our result. *Real World Applications, Nonlinear Anal.*, 2017; 34: 188-200].

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Competing Interests

The author has stated that there are no conflicting interests.

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